

THE ANALYSIS OF RELATION BETWEEN DIFFERENT VARIABLES AND UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' MOTIVES FOR PARTICIPATION IN SPORTSⁱ

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Abstract:

The object of this study is to determine the motives of university students who participate in physical activities during college education and examine whether the data differ according to educational background, sex and family support. A total of 100 students from the department of physical education and sports teaching participated in the study. As a data collection tool in the work, "Participation in Sport Motivation Scale", Gill et al. (1983), translated into Turkish by Çelebi (1991) and published by Oyar et al. (2001) have been used for validity and reliability between the studies in the age of 11-17^(6,13). In the study, reliability was checked again for this group and reliability coefficient was 0.86 in Cronbach Alpha internal consistency test. The most important motive for participation in sports for university students in the study has been found to be "skill development" and "movement/activity". In the consequences related with the motives of individuals for participation in sports, because the average for each sub-dimension is high, differences within these averages can be a determining factor in the preparation of the activities, plans and programs to be carried out and more and willing participation of the individuals in their physical activity.

Keywords: motives for participation in sports, university students, sports

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1. Introduction and Purpose

It is known that more people participate in sports each year. Therefore, the concept of sport participation motivation has been defined as a concept to be investigated and examined and a number of studies have been carried out with the aim of defining and categorizing the reasons leading to the participation of individuals participating in sports and physical activity ⁽⁶⁾.

Over the course of nearly twenty years, many researches and evidence have been published on the health benefits of physical activity. In these surveys, the types of physical activities that are beneficial to improve physical health have been determined. ⁽¹⁴⁾ In order to find an answer to the question of what to do to turn a person's behaviour into a desired intensity and direction; it is necessary to reveal the motive behind the behaviour ⁽¹²⁾. It is therefore crucial to identify the sport aspects and the motives that students consider in sports participation. The aim of this study is to determine the perspective of university students and their motives for participation in the sport.

The concept of sport participation motivation has been determined as a concept to be analysed and examined in youth sports and a number of studies have been carried out with the aim of defining the reasons leading to participation in activities, and categorizing these reasons, mainly for individuals participating in sports and physical activity. These initial studies of sport participation motivation have revealed that skill development and learning, leisure, physical fitness, friendship, and achievement are the most important factors influencing sport participation ⁽⁶⁾. It is stated that researches carried out with sport participation motivation and the collected data will be beneficial to administrators and leaders in preparing the program, where coaches can meet the needs of the participants in the events and by identifying the needs of the individuals and directing their needs in this direction will positively affect their psychological and motor developments.

Many studies have shown that young people doing sports show less behavioural disorders, better academic achievement, better classroom behaviour, avoiding harmful habits, and developing better social relationships ⁽¹⁶⁾.

2. Material and Method

The aim of this research is to determine the motives for participation of students who are studying at university and to examine them in terms of different variables. This study was carried out on a total of 100 sample individuals, 46 female and 54 male students studying at Department of Physical Education and Sports of Kazim Karabekir Education Faculty of Türkiye Erzurum Atatürk University in 2016/2017 academic year.

Independent variables used in the research were prepared by the researcher. The study consists of the "Sport Participation Motivation Scale" developed by Gill, Gross and Huddleston in 1983 composing of 30 items and 8 sub-dimensions (Skill Development, Team Membership / Spirit, Entertainment, Friendship, Achievement /

Status, Energy Expenditure, Physical Fitness, and Other Causes). The students' reasons for participation in the sports were evaluated on a 3-point scale of "Very Important (1)", "Less Important (2)" and "Not Important (3)". As the "Sport Participation Motivation Scale" was rated between 1 (Very Important) and 3 (Not Important) at the moment, the low values obtained indicate that the article is more important. The scale was translated into Turkish by Çelebi (1993) and the validity and reliability study for Turkish students aged 9-17 years was done by Oyar, Aşçı, Çelebi and Mülazımoğlu (2001). In this study, "Sport Participation Motivation Scale", the Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient was found 0.88 in males ⁽¹³⁾.

In the analysis of the data, frequency distribution to determine the demographic characteristics T test was applied to examine the relationship between two independent variables and Anova variance analysis tests were applied to examine the relationship between two variables. LSD test was used to determine the group from which the differences originated. All these tests were analysed in the SPSS 21 package program and the level of significance was taken as $p < 0,05$. Reliability was checked again for this research group in your study and in the Cronbach Alpha internal consistency test, the reliability coefficient was determined as 0.86.

3. Findings

In this section, the frequency distributions of the demographic characteristics of the students participating in the study are given by Independent- Samples T test analysis results, which are used to determine the relationship between two independent variables and the sport participation motives and One-Way Anova test to determine the relationship between the two variables and the sports participation motive.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics Distribution of Sample Individuals Participating in the Survey

Variable		Number (N)	Percentage (%)
Sex	Female	46	46,0
	Male	54	54,0
	Total	100	100,0
Age	Age 19 and under	31	31,0
	Between the ages of 20-22	55	55,0
	Age 23 and above	14	14,0
Are you playing a different sport?	Yes	93	93,0
	No	7	7,0

Table 2: Score Averages and Standard Deviations of Sports Motivation Subscales of Female and Male Students and t Values of Differences between the Averages

Subscales	Sec	N	X	Ss	t	P
Achievement Status	Female	46	6,5217	1,84679	-1,651	,102
	Male	54	7,1481	1,92704	-1,657	

Physical Fitness Energy Spending	Female	46	6,5870	1,65430	-2,055	,043*
	Male	54	7,3704	2,08586	-2,093	
Team Member Spirit	Female	46	5,3043	1,64478	-2,003	,048*
	Male	54	6,0000	1,80147	-2,017	
Friend	Female	46	4,4565	1,31160	-,966	,337
	Male	54	4,7222	1,41976	-,972	
Fun	Female	46	5,0435	1,49006	-2,447	,016*
	Male	54	5,8704	1,83310	-2,488	
Competition	Female	46	3,6304	1,10270	-2,219	,029*
	Male	54	4,1667	1,28489	-2,246	
Skill Development	Female	46	3,6522	1,26872	-1,108	,270
	Male	54	3,9444	1,35168	-1,114	
Motion – Being Active	Female	46	3,4130	,71728	-3,160	,002*
	Male	54	4,1852	1,51812	-3,327	

When the relationship between the averages of the points that the female and male students get from the sport motivation subscales is examined according to the level of significance $p: 0,05$, significant differences were found in physical fitness, energy expenditure, team member spirit, fun, competition, and motion. In terms of physical fitness, energy expenditure, team member spirit, fun, competition and movement activity subscales, male students' average scores were found to be higher than female students.

In the sub-dimensions of achievement status, friend and skill development, there was no significant difference between students' genders.

Table 3: The Average of the Scores of the Individuals in Different Age Groups on Sports Participation Motive Subscales and Anova Variance Analysis Values of the Differences Between the Standard Deviations and the Averages

Subscales	Age	N	X	Ss	f	P
Achievement Status	Age 19 and under	31	6,9355	2,11243	,178	,594
	Between the ages of 19 - 22	55	6,7636	1,75292		
	Age 23 and above	14	7,0714	2,12908		
Physical Fitness Energy Spending	Age 19 and under	31	6,7097	2,10069	1,527	,085
	Between the ages of 19 - 22	55	6,9818	1,64981		
	Age 23 and above	14	7,7857	2,45509		
Team Member Spirit	Age 19 and under	31	5,5806	1,97946	,966	,184
	Between the ages of 19 - 22	55	5,5818	1,55981		
	Age 23 and above	14	6,2857	1,97790		
Friend	Age 19 and under	31	4,7097	1,50982	,153	,639
	Between the ages of 19 - 22	55	4,5636	1,34390		
	Age 23 and above	14	4,5000	1,22474		
Fun	Age 19 and under	31	5,3226	1,93885	,350	,410
	Between the ages of 19 - 22	55	5,5091	1,57377		
	Age 23 and above	14	5,7857	1,88837		

Competition	Age 19 and under	31	4,0968	1,39892	,553	,338
	Between the ages of 19 - 22	55	3,8727	1,15557		
	Age 23 and above	14	3,7143	1,13873		
Skill Development	Age 19 and under	31	3,7097	1,27000	,128	,628
	Between the ages of 19 - 22	55	3,8545	1,35289		
	Age 23 and above	14	3,8571	1,35062		
Motion – Being Active	Age 19 and under	31	3,8387	1,36862	,816	,205
	Between the ages of 19 - 22	55	3,7273	1,09637		
	Age 23 and above	14	4,2143	1,67233		

It was determined that there was no significant difference when the scores of the students in different age groups were compared according to the mean scores of the sport motive subscales according to p: 0,05 significance level.

Table 4: The Average Scores of Students from Different Sports Situations and Sports Motivation Subscales and T Values of Differences between Standard Deviations and Averages

Subscales	Playing Sports	N	X	Ss	t	p
Achievement Status	Yes	93	6,6882	1,68741	-3,462	,001**
	No	7	9,1429	3,13202	-2,051	
Physical Fitness Energy Spending	Yes	93	6,8495	1,85886	-3,166	,002*
	No	7	9,1429	1,67616	-3,463	
Team Member Spirit	Yes	93	5,5699	1,66419	-2,334	,022*
	No	7	7,1429	2,41030	-1,696	
Friend	Yes	93	4,5376	1,33969	-1,673	,097
	No	7	5,4286	1,61835	-1,420	
Fun	Yes	93	5,4194	1,65058	-1,501	,137
	No	7	6,4286	2,50713	-1,048	
Competition	Yes	93	3,7957	1,12828	-3,952	,000**
	No	7	5,5714	1,39728	-3,283	
Skill Development	Yes	93	3,6882	1,15136	-3,569	,001**
	No	7	5,4286	2,22539	-2,049	
Motion – Being Active	Yes	93	3,7742	1,22589	-1,612	,110
	No	7	4,5714	1,71825	-1,205	

When the relationship between the mean scores of the students who play different sports and do not play sports according to the sport motivation subscales is examined according to p: 0,05 significance level, a significant difference was found in the sub-dimensions of achievement status, physical fitness energy spending, team member spirit, competition and skill development. Students who did not perform a different sport in achievement, physical fitness energy expenditure, team membership spirit, competition and skill development subscales were found to have higher scores than the students who play different sports.

In the sub-dimensions of friendship, entertainment and movement activity, it was found that there was no significant difference between different sports situations of students.

4. Discussion and Conclusion

This study investigates the different variables of participation motives of students with different demographic characteristics in the Physical Education and Sports Department of the University.

The relationship between the gender of the students and the mean score of the sprinter participation motive subscales was found to be significantly different in terms of physical fitness energy expenditure, team member spirit, entertainment, competition and motion being active sub-dimensions when examined according to $p: 0,05$ significance level. Male students' average scores were found to be higher than female students in the subscales of physical fitness depends on of physical fitness energy expenditure, team member spirit, entertainment, competition and motion being active sub dimensions. No significant difference as determined in the sub dimensions of achievement status, friend and skill development between students' genders. These findings, which greatly support the findings of this study, are supported by a number of research findings that demonstrate gender differences in the motivation of sport participation. ^(3,7,13,10).

It was determined that there was no significant difference when the scores of the students in different age groups were compared according to the mean scores of the sports motivation subscales according to $p: 0,05$ significance level. It is thought that the internal motivation of people decreases as age progresses ⁽⁹⁾. As age increases, participation appears to be more extrinsic. It is stated that the main reason for this is external awards. The external rewards that the person receives during the activity cause the internal motivation to weaken. Working to get a prize leads to the exchange of reinforcements. If the person gets the internal prizes (like the satisfaction he gets when he achieves his goal) and also receives an external prize for his achievements, external reinforcement may start to hold and may no longer have an effect on personal satisfaction as an incentive. If prizes are the reason for the activity, the person will tend to behave only when there are prizes ⁽¹⁷⁾. There are both studies that support these results, and partly similar studies ^(2,7,8,10,1,5,15,4).

When the relationship between the students who are playing sports with students who play different sports and who do not play any sports are analysed with $p:0,05$ level of significance, significant difference was determined in the subscales of achievement status, physical fitness energy spending, team member spirit, competition and skill development. Students who did not perform a different sport in achievement, physical fitness energy spending, team member spirit, competition and skill development subscales were found to have higher scores than the students who play different sports. In the sub-dimensions of friendship, entertainment and motion – being

active, no significant difference between different sports situations of students was found. Researches have in general revealed that adolescents have several factors in sports involvement. These include recreation (fun pursuit of enjoyment in sports participation), form (motivation to be healthy and physically fit), talent development (development of new talent or promotion of old talent), achievement (achievement motive in fulfilled works), status (motive of recognition and award winning), being with the team (being a team member and being motivated to enjoy the team atmosphere), friendship (motivation to be with friends), energy release (motivation to do something to get rid of excess energy) and situational motives (family, coaches and beneficial organizations) (5,18,11). As a result of these motives, the individual can also perform extra sporting activities to suppress these motives.

It is suggested for other researches to be done that sportsmen, students and individuals in different stages of the sport should be involved in sport activities and to identify elements that will positively cause sports to satisfy different motives.

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